

***Caenorhabditis elegans* and the Effects
of Serotonin on Its Olfactory Preferences**

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Abstract

The main goal of this paper is to examine to what extent serotonin influences the olfactory system of *C. elegans* toward the natural attractant OP 50 compared to the chemoattractant diacetyl as time increases. The materials in this experiment include OP50, diacetyl, petri dishes with copper mazes, and microscopes. The control variables in this experiment were the type of worms, food source, and the amount of diacetyl/OP50. The independent variable in this experiment is time, with the dependent variable in this experiment being the number of worms that moved toward diacetyl/OP50. Research indicates that serotonin causes *C. elegans* to display greater risk-taking behavior, moving towards diacetyl in growing numbers. The variations observed in the chemotaxis index at different times indicate the degree of fluctuation in *C. elegans*' response to serotonin and its impact on olfactory preferences. Data suggests there is a low standard deviation at 15 minutes, which suggests a consistent initial response from *C. elegans*. The chemotaxis index is close to 1, indicating a strong attraction toward diacetyl. The conclusion can be made that serotonin massively influences the olfactory system of *C. elegans*, making it perform greater risk-taking behaviors and increasing its attraction toward diacetyl.

Introduction/Background

Caenorhabditis elegans (*C. elegans*) is a free-living, transparent nematode that resides in temperate regions. (Chen et al 2005). They are unsegmented worms with long cylindrical body shapes that survive by consuming microbes such as bacteria. There is a substantial gap in knowledge regarding the human brain's behavioral activity and factors that stimulate decision-making. Thus, the significance of this experiment is widespread; learning about *C. elegans* and their behavioral decisions within the maze assays can help increase knowledge regarding the human brain. Studying *C. elegans* is vital because 41% of worm genes have human homologs and it's a model organism, making them easy to comprehend (Lai et al 2000). Serotonin was used because it has many effects on *C. elegans*, inducing a temptation to display greater risk-taking behavior. Serotonin also improves the olfactory preferences of *C. elegans*, making them more aware of detecting and responding to external factors. This experiment examines the neurotransmitter serotonin's effects on *C. elegans's* ability to detect food sources and differentiate common responses to environmental toxins. (Evotek, n.d). This experiment hopes to answer the question, how does time affect serotonin influence on olfactory preferences for *C. elegans*, and how will it change the number of worms that move towards OP50 or diacetyl? The independent variable in this experiment is time, with the dependent variable being the number of worms that moved to the OP 50/diacetyl. The hypothesis is if serotonin is administered to the worms, the dosed worms will more efficiently detect and move toward the diacetyl in greater numbers compared to the non-dosed worms because serotonin will increase attraction towards the chemoattractant diacetyl. It is also believed that the non-dosed worms will still move more significantly to the diacetyl than the OP 50. The controlled variables in this experiment are the type of worms, food source, and the amount of diacetyl/OP 50 used because they stay consistent.

Furthermore, the confounding variables include the risk of contamination and age because they influence the independent and dependent variables.

Measurements were conducted to determine the amount of non-dosed and dosed *C. elegans* nematodes that moved towards the OP 50 and diacetyl. This was done to examine the influence serotonin had on *C. elegans*'s olfactory presence, specifically, whether it directly impacted *C. elegans*'s ability to detect external factors such as toxins/ bacteria. Copper was used in the agar plate because *C. elegans* has a natural aversion to copper, ensuring it doesn't exit the maze. Likewise, researchers in a similar research paper discuss how *C. elegans* modifies its

Figure 1; The hypothesized choice indices for the worms

olfactory preferences after exposure to pathogenic bacteria (Zhang, Lu, & Bargmann, 2005). Zhang and others concluded that *C. elegans* avoided odors from pathogenic bacteria while simultaneously increasing its attraction to nonpathogenic bacteria. They found that exposure to pathogenic bacteria increases serotonin, which promotes aversive

learning. The increase in serotonin was found to release a negative stimulus in *C. elegans* olfactory preference, helping it improve responses to food sources and environmental toxins. Figure 1 to the left represents the hypothesis.

Method

The materials in this experiment include OP50, diacetyl, petri dishes with copper mazes, and microscopes. These materials were crucial for the experiment to be cultivated accurately.

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Description of Materials:

Figure 2: *Escherichia coli* is a group of bacteria that can cause infections in your body.

Role: It is a model organism on which serotonin has a significant influence.

Figure 3: OP50.

Role: It is the primary food source of the worms (*E. coli* strain)-worms are attracted to it.

Figure 4: Diacetyl is an organic chemical compound used to make flavors.

Role: It is a chemoattractant that produces odors that heavily attract the worms.

Figure 5: Petri dishes painted with copper mazes are cylindrical containers used in microbiology.

Role: Petri dishes with the mazes were used to study worm movements toward food sources.

Figure 6: Microscopes are laboratory instruments used to examine objects that are too small for the naked eye.

Role: Microscopes allowed us to analyze the worms that moved towards OP 50/diacetyl.

Control Variables (CVs):

Role: Improves the experiment's validity by limiting the influence of extraneous variables.

- 1) Type of worms

Representation: *E. coli* (Figure 2) was used to measure how serotonin influenced olfactory presences.

2) Food Source

Representation: OP50 (Figure 3) and Diacetyl (Figure 4) were used to determine the direction in which *E. coli* would travel.

3) Amount of diacetyl/OP50

Representation: The amount of Diacetyl/OP50 in the agar was constant to produce accurate results on the effects of serotonin.

Independent Variable (IV)

Role: It is changed to observe their influence on the olfactory presence of *C. elegans*.

IV: Time:

Description: Time is the independent variable in this experiment. As time progresses, the dependent variable changes. The variable time stands alone and isn't changed by the other variables.

Dependent Variable (DV)

Role:

DV: Number of worms that moved to the OP50/diacetyl

Description: It is measured to understand how serotonin affects the olfactory system of *C. elegans*, influencing their movements toward OP50/diacetyl.

Contamination Concerns:

Contamination is a tremendous concern because it could introduce extraneous variables that could confound the results and create inaccurate conclusions. To address this, the steps listed below were taken.

- 1) Sterile techniques were employed.
- 2) Separate pipettes were used.
- 3) The experiment was conducted using gloves and other proactive measures to prevent contamination.

Procedure

- 1) OBTAIN 2 tubes of S-buffer and two large transfer pipets from your instructor. LABEL 1 tube and pipet as "non-dosed" and 1 tube and pipet as "dosed".
 - 2) OBTAIN 2 source plates (one of "non-dosed" worms and one of "dosed" worms).
 - 3) Using the "non-dosed" pipet, TRANSFER 1.5 mL of S-buffer to the non-dosed plate.
 - 4) DISLodge non-dosed worms by rinsing the dish several times. RINSE the dish by either (a) swirling the plate or (b) holding the plate at a slight angle and allowing the buffer to pool near the bottom. Next, suck up the buffer using the "non-dosed" pipet and then expel the buffer near the top so that the buffer runs down the plate. Once worms are suspended in the buffer, TRANSFER them to the "non-dosed" tube.
 - 5) REPEAT steps 9-10 for the "dosed" worms using the "dosed" transfer pipet and plate.
 - 6) WAIT 5 minutes to allow worms to settle to the bottom of the tubes. While waiting, continue with the following steps.
- NOTE: Worms can be left for up to 24 hours in the S-buffer. Store the tubes at room temperature.
- 7) While the worms are settling, ADD 5 L of NaN_3 , to the two locations you have chosen for diacetyl and OP50. The NaN_3 , will paralyze the worms at the site of the attractant for easy counting! Refer to Appendix B for help with placement of NaN_3 , and chemoattractants. Remember that two plates will have chemoattractants inside of the maze, and the other plates have the attractants outside of the maze.

- 8) CHECK to ensure the worms have settled at the bottoms of their tubes. For both the non-dosed and dosed tubes, REMOVE and discard ~1.2 mL of the supernatant, leaving approximately 0.1 mL of buffer behind.
- 9) Using a fresh pipette tip, PIPETTE the collected non-dosed worms up and down briefly to resuspend and ADD 10 uL of non-dosed worms to the designated spot on the 2 "non-dosed" mazes. Using a fresh pipette tip, REPEAT this procedure to ADD 10 pL of the "dosed" worms to the 2 "dosed" mazes.
- 10) ADD 10 uL of the chemoattractant solutions (OP50 & diacetyl) on top of the NaN_3 , you added to your mazes in step 13.
- 11) ALLOW the S-buffer to absorb into the NGM, once this happens, the worms will be able to move about the maze. It will typically take 5-10 minutes for the S-buffer to fully absorb.
- 12) OBSERVE the worms after 15 minutes, 30 minutes, 45 minutes, and 60 minutes*. Worms can also be observed after 24 hours*. COUNT the number of worms at each experimental spot for all mazes. RECORD in your lab notebook. NOTE:
Leave the maze plates at room temperature! Do not refrigerate them once the worms are added!

Counting and chemotactic index:

The data collected (number of *C. elegans* in a given area) was made possible through a microscope at 40x magnification. Worms were counted using an accurate estimate, with a +/- five range implemented. This range was used to ensure that the number of worms was precisely counted and to prevent possible calculation errors. The chemotactic index was determined by subtracting the number of worms in the attractant area from the number of worms in the control area, followed by dividing this difference by the total number of worms on the plate.

Results

Chemotaxis Index (CI) calculations:

Actual Data

Time	Food	ND In	ND Out	D In	D Out
15 min	OP50	7	9	3	9
	Diacetyl	12	10	11	18
24 hrs	OP50	10	12	17	17
	Diacetyl	15	20	29	25
48 hrs	OP50	14	24	22	21
	Diacetyl	22	31	35	31
60 hrs	OP50	17	28	26	25
	Diacetyl	26	37	41	38

Total Number of worms = 100

Final CI:

ND In (18.75-12)/100 = **0.0675**
 ND Out (24.5 -15.75)/100 = **0.0875**
 D In (29-17)/100 = **0.02**
 D Out (28-18)/100 = **0.1**

CI = (# of worms at the attractant - # of worms at control) / total # of worms on the plate

	ND In	ND Out	D in	D Out
# of worms at control	12	15.75	17	18
# of worms at attractant	18.75	24.5	29	28

Figure 7: Calculations of CI for 4 data points (15 min, 24 hrs, 48 hrs, and 60 hrs.)

Data:

Figure 8: CI Representation

Figure 9: Experiment

Results

Graph Justifications:

Figure 8:

Figure 8 represents the Chemotaxis Index of the conducted experiment. A high chemotaxis index, which can be defined as close to 1, indicates that the diacetyl acts as a strong attractant. The bar graph visualizes this attraction standard as not too high, as the

results are closer to 0 than 1. A bar graph was needed to represent the Chemotaxis Index's applications regarding diacetyl and its level of attractiveness.

Figure 9:

Figure 9 concludes the results of the experiment, showing *C. elegans* attraction to the chemoattractant Diacetyl compared to OP50. A line graph was selected to visually represent how *C. elegans*, at all four measured times, was more attracted to Diacetyl over OP50; hence the graph shows a consistent upward trend. The dosed worms showed a significantly higher attraction to Diacetyl than the non-dosed worms, enforcing the idea that serotonin can modify *C. elegans*' olfactory preferences.

Furthermore, in the control group, *C. elegans* displayed behaviors of no risk, mostly staying within the copper walls and leaving the diacetyl outside. However, the serotonin-dosed group embodied a significantly higher risk-taking behavior, plunging through the copper walls to reach the attractant diacetyl. Figure 9 & 10 below shows a visual representation of *C. elegans*' movement towards diacetyl at 48 hours.

Figure 10: 48 hours, dosed inside Figure 11: 48 hours, non-dosed inside

Interpretation of Processed Data:

The table in Figure 7 and the line graph in Figure 8 show how serotonin-dosed worms moved quicker towards the chemoattractant diacetyl than OP50 as time progressed compared to the non-dosed worms. In Figure 8, as the data points progress, there is a positive trend towards diacetyl compared to OP50; both the dosed worms and non-dosed worms model this trend.

Figures 9 & 10 further demonstrate this trend visually, as a higher concentration of dosed worms

moved towards diacetyl than non-dosed worms. Additionally, the growth of the chemotaxis index for the dosed worms also indicates a greater attraction towards diacetyl.

Implications:

Analyzing the standard deviation within data is crucial for understanding the consistency of this experiment's results. The variations observed in the chemotaxis index at different times indicate the degree of fluctuation in *C. elegans*' response to serotonin and its impact on olfactory preferences. Figure 9 shows a low standard deviation at 15 minutes, suggesting a consistent initial response from *C. elegans*. However, as time progresses, the standard deviation in Figure 9 becomes broader, indicating a growing variability. This could be attributed to individual differences in serotonin's effects or environmental conditions affecting *C. elegans*' behavior. However, the trend stays consistent; *C. elegans*' attraction towards the chemoattractant diacetyl grows with the presence of serotonin.

Conclusion:

Serotonin greatly influences the olfactory preferences of *C. elegans*, causing them to experience a greater attraction towards the chemoattractant diacetyl. Although the non-dosed worms also moved towards the diacetyl, the dosed worms moved at quicker rates due to serotonin's effects on *C. elegans*' olfactory preferences.

Discussion

The results of this experiment indicate that serotonin plays a significant role in modifying the olfactory preferences of *C. elegans*. The control group displayed no-risk behavior, showcasing little interest in moving toward OP50, their natural attractant. However, the serotonin-dosed worms showed more distinguished risk-taking strategies by moving through the

copper walls of the maze to reach the diacetyl, which the serotonin helped influence its olfactory preferences. Chemotaxis calculations support this conclusion by showing that attraction was greater towards diacetyl as time grew due to the influence of serotonin. Additionally, figure 9 represents the finding that the number of worms that were found near diacetyl showed a consistent increase as the dependent variable, time, increased. Given that *C. elegans* are model organisms, the conclusion can be made that the results of this experiment show a strong link that serotonin can influence organisms' neurobiology. Results indicate that the genetic composition of *C. elegans* is similar to that of humans, helping scientists learn more about human neurological reactions, too.

However, limitations of this experiment fundamentally exist. The 60-hour observation was collected at a time when most of the worms were dead from starvation, possibly deflating results. Additionally, estimates of the number of worms were taken at the first eye glance instead of individually counting them. Possible sources of error may include environmental factors such as worm health and environmental factors. Maintaining a consistent environment and ensuring the worms are constantly monitored is crucial to generating reliable results. Nevertheless, the conclusion can still be reached that serotonin can massively influence the olfactory preferences of *C. elegans*, causing them to take more risks and become more attracted to the chemoattractant diacetyl.

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